

Language and linguistics translation from English into Scandii.

Language beginning with the English word a:

English	Scandii
Abacus	Abacthana
Abandoned	Abnodna
Abdominal	Abdominal
Absolute	Absolute
Absolutely	Absolutana
Absorb	Asburba
Abstract	Astractana
Abyss	Void
Academy	Academia
Acceleration	Accelerotna
Accept	Asaptana
Access	Ascana
Accident	Ascidentana
Achieve	Ashivana
Acid	Ashidana
Acoustic	Acroestiscium
Acquaintance	Friend
Acre	Acre
Acrobatic	Acrobatic
Activate	Activatana
Adamantite	Adamantium
Add	Add
Additional	Additional
Adequate	Adequatana
Adipsia	Adipsia
Adjust	Ajoestana
Admire	Admirana
Adopt	Adoptana
Adult	Adoeltjana
Adult (that is dishonourable)	Adoeltsana
Advanced	Advanced
Adventure	Adventjana
Adventure (that is dishonourable)	Adventsana
Advise	Advijana
Advise (that is dishonourable)	Advisana
Advocate	Advocatjana
Advocate (that is dishonourable)	Advocatsana
Aerial	Aerial
Affect	Afectana
Affinity	Afluentana
Affordable	Forturohna

